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Trusted Lifetime in Operation for a Circular Economy

In ARCHIMEDES, components, models and methodologies to increase the efficiency and lifetime of the propulsion components, power components, and energy storage devices in automotive, aviation and industry will be developed

About the project

ARCHIMEDES at the **Chips JU Launch Event** in Brussels
The project was represented by its own stand at the Walk of Fame Exhibition.

Presentation of **ARCHIMEDES** at **The Autonomous Main Event 2023** in Vienna during the spotlight session titled 'Autonomous Driving and Future Mobility Trends in R&D'.

More info

Coming event - **Tech Talk: Navigating the Convergence of Ecosystems**
On February 8-9, 2024 in HOTEL SB Plaza Europa, Barcelona, Spain

Chips Joint Undertaking

ECS Brokerage Event 2024

The networking event organised by AENEAS, EPoSS and INSIDE is dedicated to project proposals in the field of Electronic Components and Systems.

[More info](#)

ECOLIFE - Eco-Friendly Lifetime Extension and Mobility Initiative

Three European collaborative projects – ArchitectECA2030, EcoMobility project and ARCHIMEDES – have joined forces in a bid to amplify the influence of emerging technologies in the domains of lifetime extension and mobility.

More info

Stay tuned

ARCHIMEDES

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